

Studies on the Complexes of Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) with α -Benzilmonoxime

P. P. BHARGAVA*, R. BEMBI and MALA TYAGI

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 667

Manuscript received 25 November 1981, revised 22 April 1982, accepted 10 December 1982

Chelates of Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions with the bidentate ligand α -benzilmonoxime (α -BMOH) have been studied. On the basis of conductometric titrations, elemental analysis and molar conductivity data, the chelates have been assigned structures $[\text{Cr}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_3]$, $[\text{Mn}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$, $[\text{Fe}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_3]$, $[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$, $[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$. Magnetic susceptibility and absorption and infrared spectra of the chelates are reported and discussed. The magnetic moment studies provide evidence for the existence of octahedral Cr(III) and Fe(III) complexes and square planar Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes.

SEVERAL transition metal complexes of different oximes have been reported¹⁻⁵ and characterised.

A survey of literature shows that not much work has been done on monoxime complexes derived from diketones. Monoximes of α -diketones are also very important gravimetric reagents. Metal oxime reaction leads to quantitative precipitation and colour formation of many metal ions under different conditions, leading to successful determination of the metal ions. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile to carry out physico-chemical studies on the reactions of α -benzilmonoxime (α -BMOH) with some transition metals. Tentative structures have been proposed for the chelates on the basis of spectral, magnetic susceptibility, chemical analysis and molar conductivity data. The findings are reported in this paper.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of 'AnalaR' or chemically pure grade.

Preparation of ligand: α -BMOH was prepared by the method reported in the literature⁶.

Preparation of metal-chelates: For the preparation of their chelates Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III) and Cu(II) were used in the form of chlorides, while Ni(II) and Co(II) were in the form of sulphates. Solutions of metal salt, except Co(II), and the ligand were prepared in methanol while the solution of Co(II) sulphate was prepared in 1 : 1 methanol-water mixture.

A methanolic solution of Fe(III) or Cr(III) salt was gradually added with stirring to a methanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 3 (M : L) molar ratio, while in the case of Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II), the metal salt was added to the ligand in 1 : 2 (M : L) molar ratio. The complexes were obtained at

different pH (Table 1). The solution was concentrated on water bath for about half an hour and cooled. The precipitates were filtered, washed thoroughly first with distilled water, then with 0.05N NaOH to remove excess α -BMOH, if any, and finally with distilled water. They were dried in vacuum. The results of analysis of the chelates are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Complex	Colour	pH	Analysis % ; Calcd. (Found)			
				N	H	O	M
1.	$[\text{Cr}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_3]$	Dirty green	9.6	5.83 (5.80)	4.16 (4.10)	69.90 (69.80)	7.21 (6.85)
2.	$[\text{Mn}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$	Yellow	8.3	5.57 (5.55)	3.98 (3.85)	66.80 (66.55)	10.93 (10.58)
3.	$[\text{Fe}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_3]$	Blackish brown	8.7	5.77 (5.72)	4.12 (4.05)	69.25 (69.00)	7.72 (7.67)
4.	$[\text{Co}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$	Dark brown	7.9	5.52 (5.25)	3.95 (3.93)	66.30 (66.25)	11.64 (11.62)
5.	$[\text{Ni}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$	Red	10.0	5.52 (5.32)	3.95 (3.90)	66.28 (66.20)	11.60 (11.55)
6.	$[\text{Cu}(\alpha\text{-BMO})_2]$	Dull green	8.0	5.50 (5.48)	3.93 (3.85)	65.94 (65.85)	12.48 (12.40)

Physical measurements: Freshly prepared α -BMOH solution was always used for conductometric titrations. Stock solutions of metal salts were prepared in methanol and their strength determined by usual methods. Both direct and reverse conductometric titrations were performed to decide the composition of Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)- α -BMOH complexes. 'Phillips Conductivity Bridge' with a dip type conductivity cell (cell constant 1.12) was used for conductance measurements. Molar conductance of all the complexes were calculated.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out with a 'Vibrating Sample Magnetometer,

* Author for correspondence.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC DATA (AT ROOM TEMP.) AND MOLAR CONDUCTANCE IN NITROBENZENE

Sl. No.	Complex	μ_{eff} B.M. Measured (lit. value)	Coordination No.	n	Hybridisation	Stereochemistry	M^*
1.	[Cr(α -BMO) ₃]	3.82 (3.70-3.90)	6	3 (2.95)	d^2sp^3	Octahedral	0.51
2.	[Mn(α -BMO) ₂]	5.66 (5.65-6.10)	4	5 (4.70)	sp^3	Tetrahedral	0.02
3.	[Fe(α -BMO) ₃]	2.10 (2.0-2.5)	6	1 (1.33)	d^2sp^3	Octahedral	0.67
4.	[Co(α -BMO) ₂]	2.24 (2.2-2.5)	4	1 (1.44)	dsp^2	Square planar	0.02
5.	[Ni(α -BMO) ₂]	0	4	0	dsp^2	Square planar	0.23
6.	[Cu(α -BMO) ₂]	1.73 (1.70-2.20)	4	1 (0.93)	dsp^2	Square planar	0.07

M^* = Molar conductance ($\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$) in $10^{-3}M$ solution of nitrobenzene at 25°.

TABLE 3—INFRARED SPECTRAL DATA OF LIGAND AND CHELATES

			Cr(III) Complex	Mn(II) Complex	Fe(III) Complex	Co(II) Complex	Ni(II) Complex	Cu(II) Complex
OH or NO - H	Stretching	2900	—	—	—	—	—	—
C - N	Stretch	1610 (s)	1605 (ms)	1605 (ms)	1600 (s)	1600 (s)	1600 (s)	1590 (mbd)
N - O	Stretch	985 (m)	920 (ms)	970 (ms)	980 (ms)	930 (ms)	920 (ms)	940 (ms)
C - O	Stretch	1310 (s)	1330 (ms)	1320 (ms)	1320 (ms)	1320 (m)	1330 (m)	1320 (mbd)
OH	Phenolic	3060 (m)	—	—	—	—	—	—

m = Medium
s = Sharp
bd = Broad

Model-155⁹. The observed molar susceptibilities were corrected for diamagnetic contributions⁷. The results are given in Table 2.

Infrared spectra of Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of α -BMOH were taken in the KBr medium using Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer. The principal assignments for respective metal-complexes and ligand are given in Table 3.

Visible and ultraviolet spectra of the complexes were recorded on 'Specord UV VIS' spectrophotometer in methanol and chloroform solutions.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes described here are sparingly soluble in organic solvents and insoluble in water and dilute alkali solution. The molecular weight of the complexes could not be determined because of their limited solubility in common organic solvents employed. They are non-ionic⁸ in nature as indicated by their molar conductance in nitrobenzene solution ($\sim 10^{-3}M$), which varies from 0.02 to 0.1 mhos.

Conductometric titrations show sharp breaks corresponding to the metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 2 for Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) and 1 : 3 for

Cr(III), Fe(III). The ratios are further supported by pH metric titrations and the results of chemical analysis (Table 1).

The results of the magnetic measurements presented in Table 2 throw light on the stereochemistry of these complexes. The magnetic moment for the Fe(III) complex, [Fe(α -BMO)₃], was found to be 2.10 B.M. which is in fair agreement for low spin (d^2sp^3) octahedral Fe(III) complex, while the Cr(III) complex, Cr(α -BMO)₃, showed a magnetic moment of 3.82 B.M. corresponding to the high spin (d^2sp^3) octahedral Cr(III) complex.

In the case of Mn(II) complex, [Mn(α -BMO)₂], the magnetic moment was found to be 5.66 B.M. corresponding to the high-spin (sp^3) tetrahedral Mn(II) complex.

The Ni(II) complex, [Ni(α -BMO)₂], was found to be diamagnetic while the Co(II) and Cu(II) complexes showed magnetic moments of 2.24 and 1.65 B.M. corresponding to one unpaired spin. This indicates a square planar configuration (dsp^2) for the Ni(II), Co(II)⁶ and Cu(II) complexes.

The infrared spectrum of complexes are practically identical. The frequency of some significant bands of the free ligand and of the metal complexes are reported in Table 3. The assignments for frequencies of the different groups in the metal complexes corresponding to those considered for ligand

have been proposed tentatively on the basis of literature data¹⁰⁻¹².

Examination of ir spectrum of the complexes shows that phenolic hydrogen is replaced by metal because the band at 2900 cm⁻¹, due to -OH group of oximate moiety, appears more or less at the same position in the ligand and the complexes, and the 3060 cm⁻¹ peak of phenolic -OH disappears in the complexes. A weak maxima at 1610 cm⁻¹, assigned to C=N grouping is shifted by 10-20 cm⁻¹ in complexes and its intensity is also reduced. The medium peak at 985 cm⁻¹ in the ligand assigned to N-O stretching vibrations, shifts between 985-920 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. These changes in the absorption frequencies for C=N group and N-O stretching vibrations confirm the donation of a lone pair from the nitrogen to the metal to form chelates.

All these complexes exhibit a number of peaks in the region 650-250 cm⁻¹. However, their assignments are difficult because the ligand also reveals a series of bands in the same range.

The electronic spectral data for ligand field transitions are summarised in Table 4. Cr(III) complex shows only one band around 17,500 cm⁻¹ and also a charge transfer band at 38,250 cm⁻¹, which is in good agreement with the values for octahedral Cr(III) complexes reported in the literature^{1,3}.

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BAND AND THEIR PROBABLE ASSIGNMENTS

Sl. No.	Complex	Spectral band cm ⁻¹	Assignments
1.	[Cr(α-BMO) ₃]	17,500	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)
		38,250	⁴ A _{2g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P) + C-T
2.	[Mn(α-BMO) ₂]	24,500	⁴ T ₁ → ⁴ A ₁
		36,000	C → T
		33,000	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
3.	[Fe(α-BMO) ₃]	39,500	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F)
		47,000	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) + C-T
		24,500	³ A _{1g} → ³ E _g
		27,500	³ A _{1g} → ³ B _{2g}
4.	[Co(α-BMO) ₂]	39,000	² A _{1g} → ² E _g + C-T
		21,000	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _g
		24,200	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2u}
		27,200	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1u} + C-T
		36,600	
6.	[Cu(α-BMO) ₂]	16,500	³ B _{1g} → ² A _{1g}
			³ B _{1g} → ² B _{2g}
		38,000	³ B _{1g} → ² E _g + C-T

Mn(II) complex shows maximum absorption at 24,500 cm⁻¹ and a charge transfer band at 36,000 cm⁻¹, indicating that Mn(II) complex is tetrahedral. In tetrahedral fields, the transitions are still spin-forbidden but are no longer parity forbidden. Thus, the tetrahedral compounds are somewhat more coloured, usually pale yellow-green¹⁴.

The electronic spectra of Co(II) complex show π-π* transition in the ligand near 39,000 cm⁻¹. The two maxima at 27,500 and 24,500 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to metal→ligand charge transfer transitions ²A_{1g} → ²E_g, ²A_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²A_{1g} → ²E_g, respectively¹⁵.

In Fe(III) complex, three bands are observed at around 33,000, 39,500 and 47,000 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the transition ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P), ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(F) and ⁶A_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}(F), respectively¹³.

The spectra of Ni(II) complex in chloroform solution shows π→π* transition in the ligand near 36,600 cm⁻¹. The two maxima at 27,200 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to metal→ligand charge transfer ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1u}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2u} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_g in diamagnetic square planar Ni(II) complex involving π-bond¹⁶.

Though three transitions, ³B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ³B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ³B_{1g} → ²E_g are expected for Cu(II) complexes, they are very close in energy and often give rise to one overlapping broad band. Sacconi¹⁷ and Meek and Ehrhardt¹⁸ observed that square planar complexes have a complex broad band at relatively higher frequencies (16,500 cm⁻¹).

On the basis of spectral, magnetic and other studies the following structures could be assigned to these metal complexes :

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M. T.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of a Research Fellowship.

References

1. M. BOYTSKY and E. JUNGRIES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1956, **3**, 38.
2. C. F. LIV and C. H. LIV, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **83**, 2515.
3. B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 224.
4. ASHA KAPARI, K. B. PANDHYA and R. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14A**, 444.
5. A. CHAKROVORTY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **13**, 1.
6. A. I. VOGELI, "A Text Book of Quantitative Organic Analysis", Longmans Green and Co. Ltd., London, 1964, p. 720.
7. PIERRE W. SELWOOD, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience Publishers Ltd., London, 1956.
8. SUTTON, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1959, **12**, 122.
9. F. A. COTTON, (Ed), "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", Interscience Publishers Ltd., New York-London, 1963, Vol. 6, p. 187.
10. I. CHARALANBONS and M. J. FRAZER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 2361.

BHARGAVA, BEMBI & TYAGI : STUDIES ON THE COMPLEXES OF Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II) ETC.

11. P. C. TRIVEDI and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 81.
12. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1979, Part III.
13. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Field", London, 1976, p. 222.
14. ANTHONY HARRIMAN, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1979, **28-30**, 147.
15. PASHUPATI P. SINGH, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **31-33**, 46.
16. H. B. GRAY and C. H. BALHAUSEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 260.
17. L. SACCONI and M. CLAPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
18. D. W. MEEK and S. A. EHRHARDT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 584.